

OPERATIONALIZE THE CONCEPT OF NEEDS IN THE CONTEXT OF GOVERNMENT WELFARE POLICY IN INDONESIA

Sunarti - Doctoral Science in Management - ITB

There are a lot of things that lead someone to do a certain behavior in which motivation and environment are two parts of those (Maslow, 1970: p. 29). According to Maslow, people are motivated by needs for various things such as food, safety love and so forth. In the context of government welfare policy, the concept of needs can be operationalized as the reason that motivates government to pursue welfare state for the citizens by fulfilling the constituent's need. Maslow's built a motivation theory that is able to give a clear explanation about how a government decides their welfare policies and how they decide which of the programs are more prioritized than others. It can also explain why a country has different priority with others even though the main goals of the programs are the same, to make their citizens happy (LiveStories, 2016: p. 4).

This essay tries to operationalize the concept of needs based on Maslow's hierarchy of needs in the context of government welfare policy in Indonesia. It will be explained about some Indonesia government policies to reach welfare society and there will be explanation of every program which is run in order to satisfy citizen's needs. The discussion will be based on the type of needs and what programs are provided to fulfill those needs. The focus of the needs discussed are the basic (physical) needs, security and safety needs and esteem needs. There is no explanation about love and belonging needs and self-actualization need because it seems that there is no certain program which is intended to specially satisfy those needs.

Maslow's Hierarchy Concept of Needs

To understand the priority of government welfare policy, let's take a look the basic concept of the hierarchy of needs offered by Abraham Maslow. To explain about motivation, Maslow offered a wonderful theory that has influenced broad fields and led various studies to either examine or apply his theory. Maslow offered a critical concept to explain motivation in order to satisfy one's need. His concept is not only applicable to psychology field (Maslow's expertise) but also in other fields such as education (Turabik & Baskan, 2015: p. 1062), business and industry (Goble, 1987: p. 285; MacKenzie, 2010: p. 16) and even government policy (Baggini, 2006: p. 232 - 233). Based on Maslow's concept, there are 5 stages of needs: basic needs (physiological needs like food, nutrition, water, shelter, etc), safety needs (security, stability, health, insurance, freedom from fear, need for structure, order, law, limit etc), love and

belonging needs (love, affection, a relation to a spouse, family, friends, children, neighborhood, etc), esteem needs (education, stability, achievement, competence, freedom, status, attention, recognition, dignity, appreciation, etc) and self-actualization needs (self-fulfillment). Once a lower need is satisfied, the higher need will emerge (Maslow, 1970: p. 35-46; LiveStories, 2016: p. 13). However, it does not mean that the lower need should be satisfied fully 100% to make the higher need emerged. It only determines the percentage of the fulfillment which means the lower needs must have higher percentage of satisfaction (Maslow, 1970: p. 53-54).

Even though this concept is accepted in various disciplines, there are some critics about Maslow's concept, especially in the too simplistic methodology of the study which cannot be generalized and the hierarchy order of the need. Some studies implied that the hierarchy is not applicable to all societies, in all age stages (King-Hill, 2015: p. 55), and the level of satisfaction is different to people in the different stage of age (Seednia & Nor, 2013: p. 420). Nevertheless, the general idea of this hierarchy can give clear sense to understand needs (Baggini, 2006: p. 229) Maslow' concept of needs and motivation can be a guidance to arrange policies that make the citizens' life satisfaction reached. The primary purpose of government policy is to actualize welfare state (Situmorang, 2017). To reach it, citizens must be prosperous and there will be no prosperous citizens if the citizens are not satisfied with their overall life. Thus, applying the concept of needs to measure the welfare policy is important to give insight for the government whether those policies are effective to increase the public happiness or not (LiveStories, 2016: p. 6).

Indonesia Government Welfare Policy

According to APBN 2017, there are some focuses in order to determine the budgeting of every government program which have been decided or run. The programs planned for 2017 by Indonesia government focus to prioritize infrastructure development along with efforts to decrease poverty level and minimize the gap among regions by keeping the sustainable and healthy fiscal management (Sri Mulyani in preamble of APBN, 2017). To realize those goals, there are five expenditure policies which have been set. The first policy is to increase the quality and the effectiveness of the social protection such as PKH, KIP, KIS, Rastra and Bidik Misi scholarship. The point of this policy is to improve the distribution system and the accuracy of the data of the recipients of those programs which have been run. The second expenditure policy which has been set in APBN 2017 is to increase productive expenditure such as infrastructure development and connectivity among regions, building housing, water, sanitation, and electricity facilities. The focus of this policy is the establishment of infrastructure and facilities to support other programs. The third policy is about strengthening the execution of prioritized programs on education, health, energy and food sovereignty, marine, tourism and industry. The fourth is related to

the first policy in which it is focusing on the distribution improvement so that the programs are right on target. The last expenditure policy is to support law enforcement and stability of safety and security through eradication of drugs, terrorism activity and weaponry (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 9).

Government welfare Policy for Basic Needs Fulfillment

For programs intended to fulfill basic needs are Rastra, PKH, and housing building. Rastra (beras sejahtera) is a program to provide staple food for Indonesian society. On the concept of needs, staple food in Rastra program includes one of the basic needs which are to be the most important need for human being. Missing this need will threaten somebody's life. People who feel hungry will not think other needs such as love, self-esteem, or even their own safety (Maslow, 1970: p. 37). In order to make sure those programs are running well as expected, the government also runs some programs to increase the production of staple food such as producing more paddy, corn, salt and fish while also subsidize the seed, fertilizer and even the infrastructure needs such as irrigation channel establishment, rice field expansion (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 23). The program which focus to produce the foods directly meet people's basic need for food whereas the supporting programs which are intended to keep the production running well are considered as practical service that help people satisfy their basic needs (Baggini, 2006: p. 229-231). These practical services are such a means to an end, producing food (Maslow, 1970: p. 21).

Another program to satisfy basic need of Indonesian citizen is PKH (Program Keluarga Harapan), a Conditional Cash Transfer program for very poor household that have pregnant/breastfeeding mother and/or having toddlers or children between 5-7 who have not got to school yet and or having teenager between 15-17 who have not graduated from elementary school yet (Kemsos, 2018). PKH program is another type of practical services that is to be a means to fulfill healthy (safety need), nutrition (basic need) and education (esteem need). Considering that PKH program is reaching broader MBRs with more varied focus, Rastra is being conversed to PKH gradually so there will be no Rastra program anymore in the future (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 9). Related to housing building, kementrian PU PERA which handle housing and infrastructure building program get their budget increasing 4, 3 % from 97, 1 billion to 101, 5 billion (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 9). It is one of the proofs that Indonesia government have a concern to the basic need, a shelter, in order to make sure that Indonesia citizen specially for those with low income can satisfy their basic need.

Government welfare Policy for Safety and Security Needs

The programs which are related to safety and security needs according to Maslow's concept are JKN (Jaminan Kesehatan Nasional), KIS (Kartu Indonesia Sehat) and security and safety service. On healthy sector, there are some prioritized programs which are strengthened on the preventive and

promotion efforts while also increase the access and the quality of the health service (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 9). These two programs are under BPJS kesehatan, a public legal entity which has a duty to provide social insurance in healthy sector. It has been started since 2014 as the responsibility of Indonesian government to fulfill its citizen's need of health. There are two types of health insurance: those who can pay their own premium (using JKN) and those who cannot pay the premium (using KIS and the government will provide the funding). Even though JKN members should pay for the premium, the government ease them by offering sorts of relatively affordable premium options.

Related to the safety and security program, Indonesia government department gives the highest budget for this department among other departments though this year, though the budget is decreased 9,3 % or 108.7 billion (2016) to 108,0 billion (2017). Furthermore, police department's budget is increased from 79, 3 billion to 84 billion (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 19). The focus of this program is like what mentioned on the expenditure policy in which the government should guarantee the security and the stability of the country in order to meet the need of the citizen, feeling secured, protected and free from fear. Therefore, the budget is applied to eradicate drugs uses, destroy terrorism activity and also buy weapons for guarding. The need of safety and security cannot be abandoned because this kind of need is considered as what Maslow said: active and dominant mobiliser of organism's resources and in a certain moment, this need becomes more important than basic needs especially when the physical needs have been satisfied (even not 100%) (Maslow, 1970: P. 39).

Government welfare Policy for Esteem Needs

Indonesia government policy that relates to esteem need fulfillment is about education and all the programs related. This also considered as a means for people to meet their needs of self-esteem, self-confidence, adequacy, status and so forth. Educated people tend to be able to have all those needs, so education is considered as practical service, a means to an end, satisfying esteem need such as being more confident because someone is well educated. For education program, Indonesia government provides what is called KIP (Kartu Indonesia Pintar) and Bidikmisi scholarship. As the commitment of the government to satisfy its citizen need of esteem need through education, government decide to keep the percentage of budget for education sector on 20 % and the focus of this program is to increase the access to education facilities (APBN Indonesia, 2017: p. 9). It is clearly seen that some provinces in Indonesia especially those which are far away from a city, have very lack of facilities and infrastructures to support the implementation of education. That is why the government offers KIP and Bidikmisi scholarship in order to subsidize poor students.

After long explanation of operationalizing concept of needs in the context of government welfare policy in Indonesia, it can be concluded that Indonesia still play in the role of providing service in the

basic stages (basic needs, security and safety needs and also esteem needs) in which their absences give acute effect rather than their presence. Even though love and belonging includes basic stages of need, there is no special service from the policy, because it tends to be personal needs instead of human needs (Baggini, 2006: p. 232). The concern of government policy in Indonesia is not reaching the higher need yet, such as self-actualization and even aesthetic need. It shows Indonesia is still struggling to carry on living rather than expressing the highest aspiration as human being (Baggini, 2006: p. 232).

References

- Baggini, (2006). *Making Sense. Philosophy Behind the Headlines*. UK: Oxford University Press.
- Direktorat Penyusunan APBN, Direktorat Jenderal Anggaran. (2016). INFORMASI APBN 2017 APBN: yang lebih kredibel dan berkualitas di tengah ketidakpastian global. Jakarta.
- Goble, F. G. (1987). *Mazhab Ketiga. Psikologi Humanistik Abraham Maslow*. Yogyakarta: Kanisius.
- Kemso. (2018). Program Keluarga Harapan. <https://www.kemsos.go.id/program-keluarga-harapan>
- King-Hill, S. (2015). Critical analysis of Maslow's Hierarchy of Need. *The STeP Journal*, 2(4), 54-57.
- LiveStories. (2016). *Happy Citizens: Measuring Performance in the Public Sector*. <https://www.livestories.com/e-books/happy-citizens-measuring-performance-in-the-public-sector>
- Mackenzie, I. (2011). *English for Business Studies Third Edition*. Cambridge: University Press.
- Maslow, A. H. (1970). *Motivation and Personality (2nd ed.)*. New York: Harper & Row.
- Saeednia, Y & NOR, M MD. (2012). Measuring Hierarchy of Basic Needs Among Adults. World Conference on Psychology and Sociology 2012. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 82(2013), 417 - 420.
- Situmorang. (2017). Kebijakan Pemerintah Kaitannya Dengan Kesejahteraan. <http://www.jurnalsocialsecurity.com/news/kebijakan-pemerintah-kaitannya-dengan-kesejahteraan.html>
- Turabik, T & Baskan, G. A. (2015). The Importance of Motivation Theories in Terms of Education Systems. 5th World Conference on Learning, Teaching and Educational Leadership, WCLTA 2014. *Procedia - Social and Behavioral Sciences*, 186(2015), 1055-1063.